

Systematic studies on crystallization, microstructure and mechanical behavior of barium doped potassium mica glass

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Abstract : A barium doped glass-ceramics with the composition of $0.4\text{BaO}\cdot 0.6\text{K}_2\text{O}\cdot 4\text{MgO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 6\text{SiO}_2\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$ was prepared. Two crystallization peaks in DTA ascertain that the first one arises for the formation of K-fluorophlogopite while the second peak is for Ba-fluorophlogopite. The activation energy for the first and second crystallization temperatures are 279.2 and 326.4 kJ/mol. The decrease in hardness value with increase in machinability at intermediate temperature range is due to the formation of either potassium and/or barium fluorophlogopites phases. An interconnected 'house of cards' microstructure is developed at higher temperature region. The crystal phases like enstatite and hexa celsian, etc. are formed beyond 1100 °C.

Keywords : Glass, mica glass-ceramics, 'house of cards' microstructure, hardness.

Introduction

The thermally controlled crystallization of glasses of suitable composition ends up with the formation of fine grained polycrystalline materials¹. In the domain of fluorine mica, glass-ceramics comprising the characteristic microstructure of sheet silicates are established to be machinable, strong by thermal shock resistant with outstanding dielectric properties².

Mica based glass-ceramics are processed in many ways including sintering, centrifugal casting and melt casting. The glass-ceramics owes the machinability to its unique architectural microstructure fabricated by the randomly oriented mica platelets. However, the strength and fracture toughness of the commercial materials such as MACOR are not up to the mark in applied field³.

Henry *et al.*^{4,5} studied the effect of alumina content in the system of $8\text{SiO}_2\cdot Y\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 4\text{MgO}\cdot 2\text{MgF}_2\cdot \text{BaO}$. The result indicated that decrease in alumina content lowers the glass transition temperature as well as the first crystallization peak temperature

and promotes bulk crystal nucleation. The above authors also reported that the glasses of alumina content above 3.5% are quite common with feathery microstructures that oppose the formation of the classic 'house of cards' microstructure.

Uno *et al.*⁶ prepared the barium containing glass-ceramics like $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\cdot \text{Mg}_3\cdot (\text{Si}_3\cdot \text{AlO}_{10})\cdot \text{F}_2\cdot \text{Mg}_2\cdot \text{Al}_4\cdot \text{Si}_5\cdot \text{O}_{18}\cdot \text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and studied its crystallization and mechanical behavior by DTA, XRD and micro hardness indenter. The results were in favor of improved fracture toughness and bending strength values. The addition of tricalcium phosphate had improved the stability of the glasses prior to crystallization. Although, no specific compositional details come out from their study yet it was acknowledged that the composition had been close to the $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\cdot \text{Mg}_3\cdot (\text{Al}\cdot \text{Si}_3)\cdot \text{O}_{10}\cdot \text{F}_2$ stoichiometry.

Greene *et al.*⁷ studied the $(1-Z)\text{BaO} : Z\text{K}_2\text{O} : (6-X)\text{MgO} : X\text{MgF}_2 : (3-Q)\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : Q\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 : 8\text{SiO}_2$ systems (where $Z = 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75$ and 1.0 , $X = 2, 2.5$ and 3.0 and $Q = 0, 0.5$ and 1). The excerpt of

the work is that the substitution of barium by potassium increases the molar volume, thermal expansion co-efficient and decreases the fractional glass compactness, microhardness and glass transition temperature values.

Recent studies⁸ on the kinetics and crystal growth of the barium fluorophlogopite glass-ceramics $\text{BaO} \cdot 4\text{MgO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{SiO}_2 \cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$ with the variation of MgF_2 , illustrate that the crystallization initially being promoted by fluorine content, is largely homogenous.

Some studies⁹ on the kinetics as well as the crystallization behavior, microstructure and mechanical properties of the system $\text{Ba}_x \cdot \text{K}_{1-2x} \cdot \text{Mg}_3 \cdot \text{Al} \cdot \text{Si}_3 \cdot \text{O}_{10} \cdot \text{F}_2$ had been carried out by DTA, XRD, SEM and hardness indenter. From the results it had been concluded that substitution of potassium by barium and variation of duration of heat treatment schedule, modified the machinability and the strength of the glasses. The same work infers that fracture toughness as well as Vicker's hardness parameter increases with gradual increase in barium content lowering the machinability. Mallik *et al.*¹⁰ investigated the crystallization, microstructure and mechanical properties of the system $0.2\text{BaO} \cdot 0.8\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot 4\text{MgO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{SiO}_2 \cdot 2\text{MgF}_2$, a derivative that was formed on account of partial substitution of potassium by barium in the original glass system of $\text{K} \cdot \text{Mg}_3 \cdot \text{Al} \cdot \text{Si}_3 \cdot \text{O}_{10} \cdot \text{F}_2$. The simultaneous formation of K-fluorophlogopite and Ba-fluorophlogopite crystal phases with the development of interconnected 'house of cards' microstructure was the outcome of the work.

The above discussion has prompted us to prepare a new machinable glass-ceramics ($\text{Ba}_{0.2} \cdot \text{K}_{0.6} \cdot \text{Mg}_3 \cdot \text{Al} \cdot \text{Si}_3 \cdot \text{O}_{10} \cdot \text{F}_2$) of moderate strength at different ceramization temperatures. The present paper reports the preparation of this glass-ceramics and the systematic studies on its nucleation, crystallization, microstructure and mechanical behavior.

Experimental

Parent glass synthesis :

Analytical grade reagents were used to prepare the mother glass batch. Barium carbonate (BaCO_3), potassium carbonate (K_2CO_3), silica (SiO_2), magnesium carbonate (MgCO_3), alumina (Al_2O_3), magnesium fluo-

ride (MgF_2) and boric acid (H_3BO_3) powders were of E. Merck quality. The composition of the prepared glass batch (% in weight) reads : BaO 7.08, K_2O 6.53, MgO 18.61, Al_2O_3 11.77, SiO_2 41.62, MgF_2 14.39. To have the glass batch of better meltability and to attain interlocking microstructure with high aspect ratio in mica, an extra amount of 2.00 weight percent of B_2O_3 as H_3BO_3 has been doped in oxide composition¹¹. In an attrition mill, different reagents were properly mixed when they were melted in a platinum crucible at 1450 °C over 4–5 h. The melt was then poured into a preheated cast iron mould to build a glass block of an approximate dimension of 60 mm × 25 mm × 10 mm dimension. The glass block, after release from the mould, was then and then transferred to an annealing furnace operating at 650 °C and was left for 1 h at this temperature followed by natural cooling to room temperature.

Annealed glass block was then cut into pieces of about 1–2 mm thickness with a precision cutter (Buehler). For nucleation, these cut samples were heated at 690 °C for 2 h and subsequently up to different crystallization temperatures (800, 900, 1000, 1100 and 1150 °C) at a rate of 2 °C/min followed by keeping them at the respective temperature for 5 h for complete crystallization.

Characterization techniques :

Differential thermal analysis (DTA) :

DT40 thermal analyzer (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) with α -alumina powder as a reference material was used for differential thermal analysis (DTA). Non-isothermal experiments were performed by heating 17 mg finely ground ($\sim 75 \mu\text{m}$) glass samples, at a rate of 5, 10, 15 and 20 °C/min in the temperature range from ambient to 1000 °C. Analytical models developed independently by Kissinger and Ozawa^{12–14} were used to analyze the DTA data and to find out the activation energy for crystallization. Avrami exponent was calculated by Augis-Bennet equation¹⁵.

X-Ray powder diffraction (XRD) :

The crystallized ceramic samples were ground to $\sim 75 \mu\text{m}$ using Parkason and agate mortar. XRD experiments were performed with an X-ray diffractometer (PW1830; PANalytical) using Ni filtered $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$, X-

ray radiation with scanning speed of 2° (2θ) per minute. The diffraction pattern was recorded within Bragg angle range 10° < 2θ < 70° and phases were identified by JCPDS numbers (ICDD-PDF2 data base).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) :

The micro structural development of the different crystallized samples was observed when back scattered electron imaging (BEI) mode of the scanning electron microscope (Hitachi, S3400N, Japan) was applied. Standard procedures those end with the use of diamond paste were followed to polish the crystal surface of all the samples. The polished samples were etched by HF solution for 30 s.

Vicker's hardness (H_V), machinability (m) and modulus of rupture (MOR) :

For the study, crystallized glass-ceramic samples were mounted on resin and were finely polished after curing. The indenter was pressed onto the polished surface of the material at a load of 500 g with a dwelling time of 15 s. The size of the impression was measured using LEITZ microhardness indenter that was a carver press. The Vicker's number (H_V) is calculated from the following formula¹⁶ :

$$H_V = 1.854 P/D^2 \tag{1}$$

where, *P* is applied load (measured in kilogram-force) and *D* is length of the diagonal of the indentation (measured in millimeter).

Characterization of glass-ceramics remains incomplete without its hardness (H_V) and associated machinability (*m*) parameter those are interrelated from the following equation¹⁷.

$$m = 0.643 - 0.122 H_V \tag{2}$$

The fracture toughness (K_{IC}) is calculated using the following formula :

$$K_{IC} = 0.025 P/C^{1.5} \tag{3}$$

where, *C* is the average crack length in mm.

Rectangular bar specimens, ground and polished with 3 mm, 1 mm and 0.5 mm diamond paste, were broken in three-point bending tests (span length, 15 to 20 mm) at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min using Instron 4411 flexural testing machine. The flexural strength represents the highest stress experienced within

the material at its moment of rupture¹⁸ is measured in terms of stress. The MOR of a rectangular sample under a load in a three-point bending set-up is

$$\sigma = 3FL/2bd^2 \tag{4}$$

where, *F* is the load (force) at the fracture point, *L* is length of the support span, *b* is width and *d* is thickness.

Results and discussion

Kinetics of crystallization :

DTA curves of the prepared glass samples observed at a heating rate of 5, 10, 15 and 20 °C/min are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Differential thermal analysis plots of glass samples at varying heating rate.

Here, two distinct crystallization peaks appear in all glass samples. When the sample as a representative one, was heated at 10 °C/min the 1st peak and the 2nd peak appearing at 771 °C and 894 °C respectively shifted towards right with increasing heating rate. The isothermal kinetics of glass crystallization is studied on the basis of the Jonhson-Mehl-Avrami (JMA) equation¹⁹⁻²³.

$$x = 1 - \exp [-(kt)^n] \tag{5}$$

Here, *x* is the volume fraction crystallized at a given temperature during time *t*; *k* is the reaction rate constant and *n* is the Avrami exponent, which is a dimensionless factor depending on the nucleation process and growth morphology.

Based on Jonshon-Mehl-Avrami equation, non-iso-

thermal crystallization kinetics of glass can be described by the Kissinger and Ozawa equation¹²⁻¹⁴.

$$\text{Kissinger equation : } \ln \frac{T_p^2}{\beta} = \frac{E}{RT_p} + C \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Ozawa equation : } \ln \beta = -\frac{E}{RT_p} + C \quad (7)$$

Here, T_p is the crystallization peak temperature in a DTA curve, β is the heating rate, E is the activation energy of crystal growth, R is the universal gas constant and C is a constant.

In Fig. 2, $\ln(T_p^2/\beta)$ was plotted against $1/T_p$ and the slope of the plot is equal to E/R , from which E can be calculated based on Kissinger equation (6).

Similarly using Ozawa equation (7), $\ln \beta$ was plotted against $1/T_p$ (Fig. 3) and the slope of the plot is equal to $-E/R$, from which E can be calculated. The average E value was found to be 279.2 kJ/mol and 326.4 kJ/mol for the 1st and the 2nd crystallization peaks respectively (Table 1).

The Avrami exponent (n) can be evaluated from the value of activation energy in Augis-Bennett equation¹⁵ :

$$n = \frac{2.5}{\Delta T} \times \frac{RT_p^2}{E} \quad (8)$$

Here, n is the Avrami exponent or crystallization index and ΔT is the full width of the exothermic peak at half-maximum intensity. The Avrami exponent values of 1st and 2nd crystallization peak temperatures were

Fig. 2. Kissinger plots of $\ln(T_p^2/\beta)$ vs T_p^{-1} for (a) 1st crystallization peak temperature (T_p^1) and (b) 2nd crystallization peak temperature (T_p^2).

Fig. 3. Ozawa plots of $\ln \beta$ vs T_p^{-1} for (a) 1st crystallization peak temperature (T_p^1) and (b) 2nd crystallization peak temperature (T_p^2).

Table 1. Calculated values of activation energy and Avrami exponent

Heating rate (β) (K/min)	1st crystallization temperature T_p^1 (K)						2nd crystallization temperature (T_p^2) (K)					
	T_p^1	Activation energy (kJ/mol)			Avrami		T_p^2	Activation energy (kJ/mol)			Avrami	
		Kissinger	Ozawa	$\langle E \rangle$	exponent	$\langle n \rangle$		Kissinger	Ozawa	$\langle E \rangle$	exponent	$\langle n \rangle$
		(E_k)	(E_o)	(kJ/mol)	(n)			(E_k)	(E_o)	(kJ/mol)	(n)	
5	1028				2.75		1149				3.65	
10	1044				2.89	2.92	1167				3.80	3.9
15	1054	278.2	280.1	279.2	2.95	≈ 3.00	1179	320.3	332.5	326.4	4.00	≈ 4.00
20	1065				3.10		1195				4.15	

calculated to be 2.92 and 3.90 respectively (Table 1). This result indicates that 1st and 2nd crystallization peaks correspond to 2D and 3D crystallization processes respectively²⁴⁻²⁷.

X-Ray diffraction :

Various crystal phases identified by JCPDS Reference files are developed in all different crystallized samples. Phases like K-fluorophlogopite and Ba-fluorophlogopite are observed in all different heat treated samples (Fig. 4). A peak owing to K-

fluorophlogopite appeared at 27° and two peaks were there at 34.1° and 60.5° for both K-fluorophlogopite and Ba-fluorophlogopite at 800 °C. The sample at 900 °C, like the earlier one exhibited the same peaks of unchanged intensity except a new one assigned as a K-fluorophlogopite at 32.3°. Additional two peaks at 35.7° and 36.5° were identified for K-fluorophlogopite and those at 39.6° and 19.6° for Ba-fluorophlogopite in case of the sample at 1000 °C. At 1100 °C, two more peaks due to Ba-fluorophlogopite were seen at 17.4° and 39.6° including the existing peaks at 1000 °C.

Fig. 4. XRD patterns of glass samples at different crystallization temperatures. (BF - Barium fluorophlogopite (JCPDS Ref. file : 00-019-0117), KF - Potassium fluorophlogopite (JCPDS Ref. file : 01-076-0816), H - Alpha-hexacelsian (JCPDS Ref. file : 01-088-1050) and E - Enstatite (JCPDS Ref. file : 00-002-0546).

For the sample at 1150 °C, there is no change in number and intensity of the peaks except the increase in sharpness.

Microstructure analysis :

The SEM photographs of the ceramised samples at 800 °C invoked for the very fine submicron microstructures consisting of some blocky crystals (Fig. 5a). Samples heated at 900 °C and 1000 °C were in favour of slightly bigger blocky crystals (Fig. 5b-c) compared to those of earlier crystallized samples at 800 °C.

These intense crystals of more or less aspect ratio appeared white in the back scattered electron imaging mode. Samples at 1100 °C and 1150 °C were found to be still large size crystals but of rod shaped in appearance (Fig. 6a-b). However the aspect ratio values of the crystals at 1100 °C are higher than those for the earlier samples but are lower than those of samples at 1150 °C. In all cases, the highly siliceous residual glasses with acicular morphology provide the bed for the growth of crystals. At higher temperature, the fu-

Fig. 5. SEM photographs of ceramised glass samples at (a) 800 °C, (b) 900 °C and (c) 1000 °C.

Fig. 6. SEM photographs of ceramised glass samples at (a) 1100 °C and (b) 1150 °C.

sion of small crystals giving rise to larger ones might count the decrease in the number of crystals per unit volume and subsequently to increase the aspect ratio values. This energetically unstable configuration appears to be the driving force towards attaining the rod shaped crystals observed for the samples at 1100 °C and 1150 °C (Fig. 6a-b). These results are also in corroboration with the mechanism as proposed by Chyung *et al.*²⁸.

Vicker's hardness (H_V), machinability (m) and modulus of rupture (MOR) :

The Vickers hardness (H_V) values are reduced to a greater extent on the formation of either potassium-and/or barium fluorophlogopite phases at 800 °C compared to that of the original glass. Further heating from 800 °C to 1150 °C, the same parameter gradually decreases up to 1100 °C (Fig. 7). The hardness values increase slightly beyond this temperature up to 1150 °C, but the rate of enhancement is not only very slow but also sufficiently lower than that in case of the original glass. The fall in hardness value at a rapid rate gives a tacit support towards the development of the interconnected "house of cards" microstructure^{29,30}. The machinability parameter (m) has been theoretically calculated from Vickers hardness (H_V) values. It

is quite evident from the results that higher the hardness value, lower is the machinability parameter as shown in Fig. 7.

The results also conclude that higher the hardness value, higher is the fracture toughness. When the temperature is increased, the fracture toughness (K_{IC}) gradually decreases up to 1100 °C. The parameter increases slightly beyond this temperature up to 1150 °C (Fig. 8). At this temperature, formation of other crystal phases like enstatite and hexa celsian, etc. might account for the sudden increase in hardness and fracture toughness values. The modulus of rupture (MOR) parameter increases to a greater extent because of the development of either potassium and/or barium fluorophlogopite phases at 800 °C. When the temperature is further increased, the same parameters gradually rise up to 1100 °C, but fall slightly beyond this temperature till 1150 °C (Fig. 8). However, the decrease despite being low is sufficiently higher than that of the original glass. The modulus of rupture (MOR) of the glass-ceramics heated at 1150 °C was lower than that at 1100 °C because the barium and potassium fluorophlogopite crystals grew large (~5 μm), thereby possibly introducing large sized critical flaws³¹⁻³⁴.

Fig. 7. Variation of Vicker's hardness (H_V) and machinability (m) of glass-ceramics samples with crystallization temperature.

Fig. 8. Variation of fracture toughness (K_{IC}) and modulus of rupture (MOR) of glass-ceramics samples with crystallization temperature.

Hardness values (H_V) decrease with increasing aspect ratio of the crystal and the crystallinity of mica and concurrently the machinability parameter also increased. Glass-ceramics sample having negative values of ' m ' cannot be considered to be machinable, because they require a large threshold cutting force to initiate machining. On the other hand, samples having positive m can be machined precisely by lowering cutting speed with small cutting force³⁵⁻³⁷. Hardness (H_V) and machinability (m) were found to be very much dependent on the development of an interconnected 'house of cards' microstructure.

Conclusion

Partial replacement of potassium by barium in the original glass, $K \cdot Mg_3 \cdot Al \cdot Si_3 \cdot O_{10} \cdot F_2$ system leads to the development of two different mica crystal phases as evident from DTA, XRD and SEM. In the present study, hardness and fracture toughness are found to increase whereas machinability decreases compared to the original glass. So long as crystallization is done at higher and higher temperature, the parameters like hardness and fracture toughness become lower in trend up to 1100 °C after which they increase except machinability running in opposite direction with modulus of rupture in tow. The development of an intercon-

nected "house of cards" microstructure in combination with the aspect ratio of the crystal plays a crucial role in controlling the mechanical properties.

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